

TIME DEPENDENT DEFORMATION BEHAVIOR OF ADAPTIVE FIBER REINFORCED PLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

Fibre reinforced plastics are being used for the development of different niche products in automotive, aerospace and plant engineering industries due to their lightweight, higher tensile strength and anti-corrosion properties compared to metallic products. The further development of fibre reinforced plastics can be achieved through the integration of functional materials. Especially structurally integrated actuators based on shape memory alloys have promising property profile, which enables them to be used for compact moving mechanisms in robotics, gripper or damping structures. This paper reports on the time dependent deformation behaviour of adaptive fibre reinforced plastics. An exemplary representation of adaptive fibre reinforced plastics - adaptive pleated fibre reinforced plastics is described in this work. The adaptive pleated fibre reinforced plastics is realized by the structurally integration of shape memory alloys actuator in a reinforcing fabric during the weaving process. Then, they are infiltrated by the thermosetting resin system. The time dependent deformation behaviour of adaptive pleated fibre reinforced plastics is characterized by the cyclic thermal induced activation of shape memory alloys. Results show that the maximum deformation of the investigated adaptive pleated fibre reinforced plastics is adjustable.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced plastics (FRP) are characterized by higher tensile strength and anti-corrosion properties compared to traditional metallic products. Consequently, FRP are used more and more for the development of different niche products in automotive, aerospace and plant engineering industries [1]. However, FRP can be utilized more efficiently and effectively by structurally integrated functional materials. Resulting functions can be lightening, defrosting, heating, structural health monitoring and actuating.

As a promising smart material for the deformation of FRP, shape memory alloys (SMA) actuator is used due to their higher specific energy density of 2000 J/kg compared to other actuator materials such as electrostatic, piezo-electric or pneumatic materials [2]. After plastic deformation, SMA returns to its

original state by thermal induced activation. Below the transformation temperature, the twinned martensite alloy is deformed plastically without damaging its crystalline structure. By thermal induced activating the detwinned SMA above its transformation temperature includes a phase change into an austenite state, which is accompanied by the regression of deformation. By cooling SMA to temperatures below the transformation temperature triggers the phase transition into martensite and thus into the initial state [3].

In recent years, the research on SMA for FRP applications gained attention to the composite community [4,5,6,7]. In previous works carried out by the authors the structurally integrated SMA for the development of adaptive FRP are shown, where SMA are embroidered on the surface of the reinforcing fabric by tailored fibre placement technology [8,9,10]. In order to minimize the further cost-intensive process stages and to efficient the adaptive FRP production, SMA have been integrated by a single-step during the production of the reinforcing fabrics [11].

This paper reports on the time dependent deformation behavior of adaptive FRP by the cyclic thermal induced activation of SMA. An exemplary representation of FRP - adaptive pleated FRP (APFRP) is described in this work. The APFRP is realized by the integration of SMA actuator in a reinforced fabric during the weaving process.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Glass Fibre-Polypropylene (GF-PP) hybrid yarn (Glasseiden GmbH Oschatz, Germany) is used for the development of APFRP. The volume fraction of GF and PP in the hybrid yarn is 70% and 30%, respectively. The fineness of the yarn is 600 tex.

A nickel-titanium (Ni-Ti) based SMA Alloy H ox. sa. (Memry GmbH, Germany) is adopted for the development of APFRP because of their good actuator quality [12]. The properties of the used SMA are listed in Table 1 [13].

Diameter (mm)	0.305
Transition temperature (°C)	95-110
Surface finishing	Oxidized (ox.)
Processing condition	Straight annealed (sa.)
Tensile strength (MPa)	1152.7
Elongation at break (%)	11.1

Table 1: Characteristics of the used Alloy H ox. sa. for the development of AHFRP.

An epoxy matrix system is taken for the infusion of the functionalized preform. A resin and hardener named MGS® RIMR 135 and MGS® RIMH 137 (Hexion a. s., Sokolov, Czech Republic) are used in a mixing ratio of 10:3. The density, flexural strength, tensile strength, compressive strength and impact strength of the used resin mixture are 1.18 g/cm³, 90 N/mm², 60 N/mm², 80 N/mm² and 70 KJ/m², respectively [14].

2.2 Weaving

A rapier weaving machine (PTS 4 / J, Lindauer Dornier, Germany) with a jacquard unit (Unival 100, Stäubli AG, Germany) is used for the flexible and fully automated production of functionalized preform, where SMAs are interlaced with weft yarns of the pleat in the warp direction. The reinforced fabric for the functionalized preform consists of two layers – upper and lower fabric layer. Pleats for the functionalized preform are produced by the upper fabric. During the pleat weaving, warp yarns for the upper and lower fabric layers are subjected to varying tension. The warp yarns for the upper fabric are tensioned differently without varying the ground warp yarn tension. Additional warp yarns are

deflected several times in their path in order to get a high warp yarn tension. The warp yarns for the upper and lower fabric are let-off in the shedding zone from the creel and warper beam, respectively.

SMA are fed in the shedding zone through a separated perforated plate. The distance between two adjacent SMA in adaptive pleated fabrics is 7.32 mm. The produced functionalized preform is shown in Figure 1. The pleat height, pleat length and the spacing between two pleats of the adaptive pleated fabrics are 14 mm, 5 mm and 142.5 mm, respectively.

Figure 1: Functionalized preform for the realization of APFRP, where pleats are shown by black rectangle boxes.

2.3 Infusion

The functionalized preform is infused by a vacuum assisted resin infusion (VARI) process. After infusion, the system is cured for 15 hours at 50°C in a laboratory oven. Then APFRP are demoulded and tailored by using a laboratory wet saw in a size of 300 mm* 30 mm. The developed APFRP is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: APFRP with structurally integrated SMA.

2.4 Characterization of time dependent deformation behavior of APFRP

A laser triangulator (OptoNCDT ILR 1401-20, Micro-Epsilon Messtechnik GmbH & Co. KG, Germany) is used to measure the time dependent cyclic deformation behaviour of APFRP. The laser triangulator is positioned on the test stand in such a way that the ray of the laser triangulator incidents at the center point (150 mm from bottom) on the sample. To characterize APFRP, one end of the narrow base plate of each sample is clamped orthogonal to the SMA-wire direction on a test stand and the other end is free. The laboratory power supply unit (type: EA-PS 3032-10 B) is used for the energy input whereby the current can be restrained. Therefore, the voltage results from the current flow and the resistance of SMA.

The heating (power supply on) for the thermal induced activation of SMA and subsequent cooling (power supply off) are executed by 1.0 A current flow and ambient atmosphere, respectively. The on and off time of the power supply for this research is taken from 10 s to 60 s with a gradient of 10 s. The test duration for each sample is 420 s. The periodic switching of the current flow is controlled by a microcontroller (lily pad). Programming of different cycle times of the microcontroller is carried out via the Arduino development environment. Wago cage clamps (WAGO Kontakttechnik GmbH & Co. KG, Germany) are used for the parallel connection of SMA. The experimental setup for characterization of APFRP is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Experimental setup for the time dependent characterization of APFRP.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The time dependent cyclic deformation behavior of APFRP from 10 s to 60 s is demonstrated in Figure 4. After the thermal induced activation of SMA, APFRP deforms subsequently. It can be concluded from Figure 4 that the cycle time of 10 s does not represent a homogeneous recovery after switching off of the power supply. The plateau width due to the heating and cooling cycle from 20 s is increased compared to the cycle time of 10 s. However, no plateau occurs during the cooling cycle of 10 s. This is due to the active heating of SMA in APFRP by the current flow and the passive cooling through the ambient temperature.

The full deformation potential of APFRP is limited by the thermal induced activation of SMA for 10 s since the maximum deformation of it is less than 20 s to 60 s. In this research, the maximum deformation of APFRP from 20 s to 60 s is 3.35 mm, and a quasi-homogeneous deformation (Δ_s) occurs above a cycle time of 20 s.

Figure 4: Time dependent deformation behavior of APFRP.

4 CONCLUSION

Time dependent deformation behaviour of adaptive pleated fibre reinforced plastics (APFRP) is presented in this paper. In order to attain this result, SMA are structurally integrated in reinforced fabrics during the weaving process. The functionalized preform is infused by the vacuum assisted resin infusion process to get APFRP. The deformation behaviour of APFRP is tested depending on the duration of thermal induced activation. The APFRP deforms partially during the thermal induced activation of SMA for 10 s. The maximum deformation of adaptive pleated FRP remains constant from 20 to 60 s.

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REFERENCES

- [1] C. Cherif, *Textile Materials for Lightweight Constructions: Technologies-Methods-Materials-Properties*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer-Verlag GmbH, 2016. – ISBN 978-3-662-46340.
- [2] P.K. Kumar, C. Caer, G. Atkinson, E. Patoor, D.C. Lagoudas, The influence of stress and temperature on the residual strain generated during pseudoelastic cycling of NiTi SMA wires, *Proceedings of SPIE 7978, Behaviour and Mechanics of Multifunctional Materials and Composites, March 7-9, 201*, 7978 1E.
- [3] K. Otsuka, CM Wayman. *Shape memory materials*: Cambridge University Press, 2002.
- [4] J.M. Jani, M. Leary, A. Subic, M.A. Gibson, A review of shape memory alloy research, applications and opportunities, *Materials and Design*, **56**, 2014, pp. 1078–1113.
- [5] A.Y.N. Sofla, S.A. Meguid, K.T. Tan, W.K. Yeo, Shape morphing of aircraft wing: Status and challenges, *Materials and Design*, **31**, 2010, pp. 1284–1292.
- [6] J.S. Shaw, J.L. Lee, Force control of a robot gripper featuring shape memory alloy actuators, *Proceedings of the International Conference on Advanced Robotics & Intelligent Systems (ARIS), Taipei, Taiwan, May 29-31, 2015*, pp. 23–28.
- [7] F. Gandhi, E. Hayden, Design, development, and hover testing of a helicopter rotor blade chord extension morphing system, *Smart Materials and Structures*, **24**, 2015, pp. 1-14.
- [8] M. Ashir, L. Hahn, A. Kluge, A. Nocke, C. Cherif, Development of innovative adaptive 3D Fiber Reinforced Plastics based on Shape Memory Alloys, *Composites Science and Technology*, **126**, 2016, pp. 43-51.
- [9] M. Ashir, L. Hahn, A. Kluge, A. Nocke, C. Cherif, Electro-bending characterization of adaptive 3D Fiber Reinforced Plastics based on Shape Memory Alloys, *Smart Materials and Structures*, **25**, 2016, pp. 035-041.
- [10] M. Ashir, A. Nocke, C. Theiss and C. Cherif, Development of adaptive hinged fiber reinforced plastics based on shape memory alloys, *Composites Structure*, **170**, 2017, pp. 243-249 (doi: 10.1016/j.compstruct.2017.03.031).
- [11] M. Ashir, J. Hindahl, A. Nocke, C. Cherif, Development of adaptive pleated fiber reinforced plastic composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, 2017 (doi: 10.1016/j.compscitech.2017.05.016).
- [12] A. Kluge, A. Nocke, C. Paul, C. Cherif, T. Linse, V. Ulbricht, Development and characterization of textile-processable actuators based on shape-memory alloys for adaptive fiber-reinforced plastics, *Textile Research Journal*, **83**, 2013, pp. 1936 – 1948.
- [13] Memry GmbH, Specification sheet, www.memry.com (15.04.2017).
- [14] Available at: <https://www.hexion.com/Products/TechnicalDataSheet.aspx?id=8246> (25.04.2016)